

ON THE DETERMINATION OF INTERLAMINAR FRACTURE TOUGHNESS OF FIBRE REINFORCED POLYMER LAMINATES USING ORTHOGONAL CUTTING

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Keywords: Fibre reinforced composite laminate, Interlaminar fracture toughness, Orthogonal cutting, Chip formation

ABSTRACT

An orthogonal cutting test method has recently been proposed for measuring the fracture toughness of low yield stress, yet tough polymers and metals. The test method is particularly useful when conventional standard toughness test pieces are difficult to obtain. In this study, experimental work has been carried out to investigate the applicability of cutting tests in determining the interlaminar fracture toughness for fibre reinforced polymer (FRP) laminates. The cutting tests were performed at a speed of 5 mm/s in the direction of the interlaminar plane on a vacuum assisted resin infusion (VARI) moulded unidirectional carbon fibre laminate. The tool rake angle was varied from 0° to 45° and the effects of tool geometry were evaluated from an analysis of chip formation, cut surface topography and cutting forces. It is found that when cutting with large rake angle tools, the chips are delaminated from the workpiece without permanent deformation or fracture. The cutting process can be analysed by use of an energy-based approach with considerations of the friction loss at the tool-chip interface, the delamination fracture along the fibre/matrix interface and the bending resistance in the chip. It demonstrated the theoretical possibility of extrapolating the interlaminar fracture toughness of the FRP laminate from the cutting tests. However, the notion is often not attainable in practice due to the intermittent nature of the interlaminar crack propagation.

1 INTRODUCTION

The enhancement of the mechanical, structural, as well as physical properties due to the addition of fibres makes FRP laminates widely used in various industrial applications, such as aircraft parts, aerospace structures, wind turbine blades, and machine parts etc. A typical FRP laminate is composed of parallel strong fibres embedded in a weaker matrix. This is to give high stiffness and strength in the plane of the sheet. However, the interlaminar plane of the laminate often has very low resistance to failure. The presence of initial voids and flaws is usually inevitable in FRP laminates arising from the manufacturing process. When load is applied, these defects may propagate along the interlaminar plane that leads to delamination. Delamination is the most common and critical mode of failure in FRP laminates. Not only can it weaken the stiffness of the laminate significantly, it may also result in a complete failure. As delamination is essentially the propagation of an interlaminar crack, the phenomenon can be characterised via a fracture mechanics approach. This has led to considerable effort to using fracture mechanics to ascertain the interlaminar fracture energies, G_c , and developing different mechanical testing methods to yield Mode I, Mode II and mixed Mode I/II values of G_c for various FRP laminates.

In fracture mechanics, the opening (Mode I) mode of fracture is most common and critical. In this case, the crack propagates by the crack faces opening perpendicular to the crack plane. The crack-tip carries all the stress and it is not affected by the interaction of the opposing crack faces like in sliding and shear modes of fracture. Double cantilever beam (DCB) test is the most popular and successfully standardised test method for measuring the Mode I interlaminar fracture energy for an FRP laminate. The analysis of the delamination crack propagation in the DCB specimen is carried out on the basis of linear elastic fracture mechanics (LEFM).

Recently, a cutting test method has been proposed to measure the fracture energies for polymers [1] and metals [2]. In this method, sharp orthogonal cutting tools with a rake angle α are used to cut surface layers of a material of varying depth h . At each cut depth, the specific cutting and transverse forces F_c and F_t are measured. The thickness of the chip produced from cutting, h_c , is also measured for the determination the shear angle φ . During the cutting process, work is required for the creation of the newly cut surface regardless the magnitude of cut depth and this can be characterised by the fracture energy of the specimen G_c [1]. There is incremental energy dissipation via friction at the tool-chip interface, S , which can be determined via [1]

$$dU_{frict} = S \frac{\sin \varphi}{\cos(\varphi - \alpha)} \cdot dx = [(F_c - bG_c) \sin \alpha + F_t \cos \alpha] \frac{\sin \varphi}{\cos(\varphi - \alpha)} \cdot dx \quad (1)$$

where dx is the tool movement and $\frac{\sin \varphi}{\cos(\varphi - \alpha)} \cdot dx$ is the displacement in the direction of the friction force, as shown in Fig. 1. It is also assumed that the chip formation is all via shear and the associated energy dissipation is [1]

$$dU_{plast} = \frac{\sigma_Y}{2} \frac{bh}{\sin \varphi} \frac{\cos \alpha}{\cos(\varphi - \alpha)} \cdot dx \quad (2)$$

in which Tresca yield criterion is used to characterise the shear stress in the chip that is equal to half of the tensile yield stress σ_Y , b is the cut width and $\frac{bh}{\sin \varphi}$ is the shear plane area, and $\frac{\cos \alpha}{\cos(\varphi - \alpha)} \cdot dx$ is the displacement in the direction of the shear. Taking these considerations into account, the total cutting energy is dissipated into frictional work, plastic energy and fracture energy, i.e.:

$$F_c \cdot dx = [(F_c - bG_c) \sin \alpha + F_t \cos \alpha] \frac{\sin \varphi}{\cos(\varphi - \alpha)} \cdot dx + \frac{\sigma_Y}{2} \frac{bh}{\sin \varphi} \frac{\cos \alpha}{\cos(\varphi - \alpha)} \cdot dx + bG_c dx \quad (3)$$

which leads to

$$\left(\frac{F_c}{b} - \frac{F_t}{b} \tan \varphi \right) = \frac{\sigma_Y}{2} \left(\tan \varphi + \frac{1}{\tan \varphi} \right) h + G_c \quad (4)$$

As a result, σ_Y and G_c can be determined from the linear plot of $\left(\frac{F_c}{b} - \frac{F_t}{b} \tan \varphi \right)$ vs. $\left(\tan \varphi + \frac{1}{\tan \varphi} \right) h$ data. The gradient gives $\sigma_Y/2$ and the positive intercept at zero cut depth on the Y-axis is G_c . It is worth noting that in order for the extrapolation method to be valid, φ needs to be constant and the values of $\left(\frac{F_c}{b} - \frac{F_t}{b} \tan \varphi \right)$ should be in proportion to the cut depth. This is viable based on the assumption that the forces of friction and shear are directly proportional to the cutting forces. To ensure that this is the case, low cutting speeds should be used to minimise the frictional heating and the strain rate effect. In addition, the α and h values need to be carefully chosen to make sure that the chip is produced by an action of shear.

Figure 1: Mechanistic model of orthogonal cutting in which chip is produced by full shear.

Experimental studies on orthogonal cutting of FRP laminates have been widely reported in the past few decades [3-5]. Primarily, much focus has been placed on issues concerning traditional machining such as surface finish, tool performance and cutting energy consumption etc. There are very few attempts to utilise cutting for determining the fracture properties of FRP laminates. This is because the cutting behaviour of FRP laminates is a lot more complex than that of polymers and metals due to their extreme heterogeneity. Discontinuous and fracturing chips are prone to be produced by highly interrupted cutting process, which makes the energy balance in terms of friction, shear and fracture difficult to perform. Obviously, the fibre orientation relative to the direction of tool advancement plays an important role [4]. When aligning the direction of cut with 0° fibre orientation, it is found that the chip formation is accompanied with interlaminar fracture along the fibre/matrix interface. Thus, it is possible to employ the aforementioned cutting theory to measure the interlaminar fracture energy of FRP laminates. This study reveals the chip formation behaviour at various tool rake angles when cutting is performed at 0° fibre orientation on a unidirectional fibre reinforced epoxy laminate. An energy-based analysis of the cutting process is presented. The practicability and challenge of the use of cutting tests in ascertaining the interlaminar fracture energy for FRP laminates are investigated.

2 EXPERIMENTAL

The FRP composite laminate used in this work was fabricated from the longitudinal carbon fibre fabrics (T300, FGI Fibre Glass International, Australia) using the VARI moulding process. Twenty carbon fabric sheets were stacked together in the unidirectional direction and sealed in a vacuum bag. A polyimide thin film (50 µm in thickness) was inserted between the 10th and 11th layers at one end of the laminate to serve as a “pre-crack” for the DCB tests. The selected matrix resin for the VARI process was diglycidyl ether of bisphenol-A (DGEBA) epoxy and the curing agent was Piperidine. The mixing ratio of the weight of epoxy to the weight of Piperidine was 100:5. When the VARI process was completed, the fully wetted fabric sheets were compression moulded in a heat press machine at 120 °C for 16 hours. A pressure of 400 kPa was applied for the moulding process and this gave a uniform laminate thickness of 4 mm.

The orthogonal cutting of the carbon fibre laminate was conducted on a CNC surface grinder (MININI M286) with the grinding head being modified where the cutting specimen can be fitted. A customised tool holder was fixed on a three-dimensional dynamometer (Kistler 9257B) which could measure the cutting forces of F_c and F_r . The tool holder and dynamometer were mounted together on the hydraulic table of the grinder that was able to provide a steady cutting motion. A group of cutting tools with rake angles of 0°, 15°, 30° and 45° were made from high speed steel and they were sharpened by means of grinding and lapping. The cutting speed was fixed at 5 mm/s and the cut depth was 100 µm. The cutting tests were performed perpendicular to the direction that the carbon fabric sheets were laid and the fibre orientation was set up to be 0° relative to the direction of cut. During cutting, the chip formation processes were observed by a digital microscope camera. In addition, DCB tests were carried out on a universal testing machine (Instron 5567) at a crosshead rate of 1 mm/min. Micrographs were taken on the delamination surfaces of the DCB specimens which were compared with those obtained from the cutting tests.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Typical micrographs obtained during orthogonal cutting along the interlaminar plane of the FRP laminate with tool rake angles varied from 0° to 45° and a cut depth of 100 µm are shown in Figs. 2a-d. It is obvious that the features of chip formation changed greatly with the variation of the tool rake angle. When cutting with small rake angle tools, the chips were created from an extreme fracture process and discontinuous in nature. Severe delamination and fibre breakage can be found in the chips, which were resulted from the in-plane shear and cantilever loading through tool advancement [4]. As the rake angle was increased, the chips tended to be produced by means of peel fracture in the cutting plane induced by the contact load at the tool/chip interface. This gave rise to chip bending. However, the process was often accompanied with interlaminar fracture in the chip, as illustrated in Fig. 2c. At a greater rake angle, e.g. 45°, the chips can be removed without deterioration of their structure integrity. In this case, the energy dissipated in the interlaminar fracture along the fibre/matrix interface was

delivered through the cantilever loading subjected to the chip, which bears a strong resemblance to the DCB test.

Figure 2: Chip formation of cutting unidirectional carbon fibre reinforced epoxy laminate at 0° fibre orientation using (a) 0° ; (b) 15° ; (c) 30° ; (d) 45° rake angle tool .

The delamination surface of the FRP laminate after cutting with 45° rake angle tool was compared with that obtained from the standard DCB test. As it is shown in Fig. 3, bare fibres are visible on both delamination surfaces with a limited degree of the epoxy matrix. For the DCB specimen, most of the fibres remained to be continuous. The fractured epoxy patterns adjacent to the fibres suggest they were lifted from the surface via Mode I loading. By comparison, the fibres presented on the cut surface were fractured perpendicular to the fibre direction. This signifies that the mechanism of chip/workpiece separation was not only composed of the Mode I fracture along the fibre/matrix interface, the Mode II in-plane shearing through tool advancement also played a significant part.

Figure 3: Micrographs of delamination surfaces obtained via (a) DCB test and (b) cutting test.

Fig. 4 depicts the specific cutting and transverse force histories during orthogonal cutting of the FRP composite using the 45° rake angle tool. It is noticed that the magnitude of the specific cutting force in the transverse direction is much greater than that in the cutting direction. In addition, the load

traces fluctuate with the advance of the cutting tool. According to the real-time observation of the cutting process, the force fluctuation is attributed to the variation of the contact conditions between the tool and the chip. This is due to the interlaminar crack propagated in a “stick-slip” manner during the chip removal process. To gain a better understanding of such cutting behaviour, it is informative to examine the curve of the specific cutting force histories periodically. At the location marked between 1.1 s and 1.8 s of the tool advancing time, the cutting forces raise to the peak due to the accumulation of the bending energy in the chip and the strain energy at the interlaminar crack front. The peaks subsequently drop as a result of the crack progression in the direction of cut. At this moment, since the cutting speed was much lower than the crack speed, the increase of the crack length gave rise to a reduction of the bending strain in the chip, which can be reflected by an increase of the chip radius of curvature from R_0 to R . The consequence of this repeating process was a series of discontinuous interlaminar crack growths which were also seen in DCB delamination tests.

Figure 4: Specific cutting force behaviour and accompanied chip formation feature during orthogonal cutting of the FRP laminate, where R represents radius of curvature of the chip and R_0 is radius of curvature at fracture point.

With the understanding of the FRP laminate cutting process, it is possible to perform a similar energy-based cutting analysis following [1] to determine the interlaminar fracture toughness. Here, shear deformation did not occur during chip formation, whereas the chip had elastic bending resistance and therefore the increment of elastic bending strain energy must be added on the right hand side of Eq. (3). The bending energy will depend upon the radius of curvature of the chip, which gives rise to a bending strain of $e_b = h/2R_0$. The elastic bending term is given approximately by [6]

$$G_b = \frac{1}{R_0^2} \frac{Eh^3}{24} \quad (5)$$

where E is the flexural modulus of the laminate and R_0 is the radius of curvature of the chip at the fracture point. Hence, Eq. (3) becomes

$$F_c \cdot dx = [(F_c - bG_c) \sin \alpha + F_t \cos \alpha] \frac{\sin \varphi}{\cos(\varphi - \alpha)} \cdot dx + \frac{1}{R^2} \frac{Ebh^3}{24} \cdot dx + bG_c dx \quad (6)$$

Because the chip thickness remains at h in the bending process, $\sin \varphi = \cos(\varphi - \alpha)$, and thus Eq. (6) can be reduced to

$$\left(\frac{F_c}{b} - \frac{F_t \cos \alpha}{b(1 - \sin \alpha)} \right) = \frac{h^3}{24R_0^2(1 - \sin \alpha)} E + G_c \quad (7)$$

Comparing to Eq. (4), in this case, the material properties E and G_c can be determined from the linear plot of $\left(\frac{F_c}{b} - \frac{F_t \cos \alpha}{b(1 - \sin \alpha)}\right)$ vs. $\frac{h^3}{24R_0^2(1 - \sin \alpha)}$ data. The gradient gives E and the positive

intercept at zero cut depth on the Y-axis is G_c . It should be noted that the mixed mode interlaminar fracture behaviour observed during cutting will give fracture energy results different to those obtained from the DCB specimens where the Mode I loading prevails. Further, to have analytical solution for Eq. (7) in obtaining the fracture energy G_c , R_0 is assumed to be constant. This can only be achieved with a steady-state delamination crack growth in the cutting process where the cutting speed and the crack propagation speed coincide. However, this is not the case in the practical cutting process as shown earlier because the chip radius of curvature differed in magnitude throughout the cutting history due to the variation of the contact conditions between the tool and the chip.

4 CONCLUSION

An experimental study of the chip formation mechanisms in orthogonal cutting was conducted on a unidirectional carbon fibre reinforced epoxy laminate at low cutting speed using high speed steel tools. Cutting tests were performed along the interlaminar plane of the laminate where the fibre orientation was 0° relative to the direction of cut. The effects of tool geometry were evaluated from an analysis of chip formation, cut surface topography and cutting forces. The purpose was to clarify the applicability of cutting tests in determining the interlaminar fracture toughness for FRP composites. Discontinuous chip formation was noted when cutting with small rake angle tools, which is not favourable to the employment of the energy-based approach to analyse the cutting process. By increasing the tool rake angle, it is possible to obtain continuous chips without permanent deformation or fracture. The cutting analysis can proceed in this case via an energy-based approach with considerations of the friction loss at the tool-chip interface, the delamination fracture along the fibre/matrix interface and the bending resistance in the chip. A linear equation has been derived which can be used to extrapolate the interlaminar fracture energy dissipation in the cutting process. It is found that the equation only applied in determining the fracture parameter when the chip radius of curvature is constant. However, this often is not attainable in practice due to the variation of the contact conditions at the tool/chip interface caused by the intermittent nature of the interlaminar crack propagation.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

We thank the Australian Research Council (DP150104160) for financial support of this project.

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